

Post-Task Usability Questionnaire

Instructions:

Each student is required to complete this questionnaire as an integral part of the assignment submission process. It captures your perception regarding the use of Large Language Models (LLMs) for modeling tasks.

Part 1: Background & Experience

Student Details:

Group Name: _____

Student ID: _____

Q01. Perceived knowledge of LLM, before the course:

None

Low

Medium

High

Q02. Experience with LLM, before the course:

None

Low

Medium

High

Part 4: Qualitative Feedback

Q05. Negative Aspects:

List the most negative aspect(s) you faced while utilizing LLMs for modeling tasks:

Q06. Positive Aspects:

List the most positive aspect(s) you faced while utilizing LLMs for modeling tasks:
